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UDK: 341.231.14-056.26/.36
UDK: 341.24-056.26/.36
UDK: 342.7-056.26/.36(438)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17942841

IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTICLE 13 OF THE CONVENTION ON THE RIGHTS OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES IN LIGHT OF THE STATE PARTY EXPERIENCES

Abstract: *The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) is the first international legal instrument to recognize access to justice as a distinct human right. State Parties to the Convention are obligated to introduce accommodations for persons with disabilities, including age-appropriate adjustments. This article analyzes the doctrinal concepts of access to justice and barriers to justice. Then, it presents various forms of accommodations introduced by selected State Parties to the CRPD to eliminate these barriers. The author also shares findings from her own research on communication barriers, conducted among judges and attorneys. The implementation of Article 13 of the CRPD remains unsatisfactory in many countries. In the author's opinion, international exchange of implementation experiences may serve as a source of inspiration for countries that have yet to introduce procedural and other accommodations to ensure effective access to justice. Notably, some effective solutions require minimal financial investment.*

Keywords: *access to justice, barriers to justice, Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, judicial process, procedural accommodations.*

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1. Introduction

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)¹ represents a landmark document in international human rights law. It redefines the status of persons with disabilities as full participants in social, political, and legal life. Of particular significance is Article 13 of the Convention which, for the first time in the history of international law, establishes access to justice as an autonomous human right (Flynn, 2016: 47). This provision not only obliges State Parties to ensure that persons with disabilities can effectively participate in legal proceedings on an equal basis with others but also implies the need for systemic reforms within the justice system, including training for judicial personnel, procedural accessibility, and appropriate support measures.

Regrettably, the implementation of Article 13 of the CRPD remains inadequate, especially among EU Member States, which ought to serve as leaders in the rule of law within this region. Somewhat unexpectedly, Ibero-American countries have emerged as frontrunners, and this article will highlight several positive examples developed in that context.

Interstate exchange of experiences is particularly valuable, as certain instruments may inspire reforms aimed at implementing Article 13 of the CRPD, while others may be directly replicated. Importantly, some of these measures require minimal financial resources yet significantly enhance the ability of persons with disabilities to access justice effectively.

As for methodology, the article first employs a doctrinal approach to decode the concepts embedded in Article 13 of the CRPD, such as access to justice, effective participation, procedural accommodations, and the notion of barriers to justice as developed in international legal doctrine. Subsequently, through comparative legal analysis, the article presents the most common and innovative instruments adopted by various State Parties to remove these barriers. Finally, it briefly outlines the author's own empirical research on communication barriers and the mechanisms designed to counteract them. This research required the application of empirical methods, including statistical analysis.

2. Concepts of Access to Justice and Effective Access in International Law Doctrine

Article 13(1) of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) constitutes the first express invocation of the term *access to justice*

¹ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution A/RES/61/106, 13 December 2006, entered into force on 3 May 2008.

within an international legal instrument, thereby affirming its status as a distinct and autonomous human right (Flynn, 2016: 47). This provision reflects a conceptual shift, recognizing access to justice not merely as a procedural adjunct but also as a right of fundamental and general value. The inclusion of this term was originally proposed by a South American state, and its adoption followed extensive deliberations spanning several months.

Notwithstanding its formal recognition in the CRPD, the normative foundations of access to justice are deeply embedded in earlier international legal doctrine. The right finds its antecedents in Articles 6-11 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights,² which enshrine the principles of equality before the law and equal protection of rights. These guarantees were subsequently elaborated in Articles 14-16 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights,³ and further codified in regional instruments such as Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights,⁴ as well as in various treaties ratified by South and Central American states.

Prior to the CRPD, the prevailing doctrinal view regarded access to justice as a procedural safeguard contingent upon the protection of substantive rights, rather than as a standalone entitlement (Palombella, 2021: 130). However, contemporary scholarship has advanced more comprehensive conceptualizations. Bahdi (2007: 5-6, 28-29, 38-39) proposes a tripartite framework comprising substantive, procedural, and symbolic dimensions. The substantive component encompasses constitutional guarantees and anti-discrimination legislation; the procedural element includes formal judicial mechanisms and alternative dispute resolution (ADR); the symbolic dimension reflects the reciprocal influence of law and society, particularly through legal education and public engagement. This tripartite model has gained traction in legal literature (Flynn, 2016: 13-19), with scholars emphasizing that access to justice entails not only entry into legal systems and procedures but also access to information and the physical infrastructure of justice (Flynn, 2016: 12, fn. 19).

An alternative definitional approach focuses on the core objectives of the judicial system, namely its accessibility and its capacity to deliver outcomes that are both individually and socially just (Garth, Cappelletti, 1978: 182). Crucially, the concept of access to justice is inherently dynamic and must be

² Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution 217 A (III), 10 December 1948.

³ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution 2200A (XXI), 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976.

⁴ European Convention on Human Rights, signed in Rome on 4 November 1950, entered into force on 3 September 1953, Council of Europe, ETS No. 5.

interpreted in light of evolving legal contexts. As Palombella (2021: 121-122) argues, the emergence of new domains of legal protection necessitates corresponding institutional responses, thereby precluding a fixed, geographically universal definition.

In the Australian context, legal scholars have identified a set of procedural guarantees that constitute the right to a fair trial. These include: equal access to and equality before the courts; the right to legal aid and representation; the right to procedural fairness; the right to be heard without undue delay; the right to a competent, independent, and impartial tribunal established by law; the right to a public hearing; and the right to free assistance by an interpreter (Flynn, 2016: 25). The UN Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities has further clarified that the procedural dimension of access to justice extends beyond trial, encompassing post-trial mechanisms and remedies.

The interdependence between access to justice and the protection of substantive rights has been underscored by Lord, Guernsey, Balfe, Karr, and Flowers (2012: 137-138), who contend that denial of access to justice may precipitate violations of other human rights. Accordingly, access to justice may function as a “preliminary” right, instrumental in securing the enjoyment of other entitlements, though not necessarily superior to them.

It is important to distinguish access to justice from narrower concepts, such as the right to a fair trial or the right to a court. While these are integral components, access to justice encompasses a broader array of considerations, including organizational, communicative, and architectural accommodations, as well as the training of judicial personnel. These elements are explicitly mandated under Article 13(2) of the CRPD. Both doctrinal commentary and reform initiatives emphasize the centrality of communication, either through technological means or human resources, in ensuring meaningful access. Procedural guarantees, though essential, must be situated within a broader socio-legal context.

Finally, Article 13(1) of the CRPD imposes a requirement of *effectiveness*. This entails that access to justice must be practically realizable, and not merely a formal entitlement. Where individuals with disabilities are unable to exercise their rights without disproportionate effort or face systemic disadvantages, the guarantee becomes illusory. For instance, the right to appeal a first-instance judgment may be rendered inaccessible for persons undergoing involuntary psychiatric treatment or elderly individuals with cognitive impairments, particularly in the absence of legal representation or exemption from court fees. Such barriers undermine the principle of equal access and may deter individuals from seeking judicial redress.

3. Barriers to Access to Justice

Although the term “barriers to access to justice” is not explicitly mentioned in Article 13 of the CRPD, it is widely used in legal scholarship and does not require formal definition due to its conceptual clarity. Scholars typically focus on typologies and examples of such barriers. Economic constraints, lack of legal awareness, and limited legal education are frequently cited (Bahdi, 2007: 33-38). Ableism – understood as defining individuals through their disability – can lead justice system actors to dismiss the credibility or autonomy of persons with sensory, intellectual, or psychosocial disabilities (Kowalczyk, 2016: 98-105). Institutional care may further hinder procedural engagement (Ruškus, 2023: 8).

Factual barriers include architectural inaccessibility and procedural requirements incompatible with a person’s mobility or cognitive condition. Communication barriers extend beyond sensory impairments to encompass the complexity and inaccessibility of legal language, especially for persons with intellectual disabilities or cognitive disorders. Semantic confusion, generational language gaps, emotional distress, and infantilizing stereotypes all contribute to exclusion. Legal barriers include complex procedural rules, preclusive norms, lengthy proceedings, and lack of support for self-represented litigants. Legal incapacitation, such as guardianship, may entirely obstruct access to justice – a concern emphasized by the CRPD.

Operational and structural barriers have also been distinguished (Abregu, 2001: 57–64). The former relate to inefficiencies within the justice system, such as poor inter-agency coordination and lack of pre-trial legal aid; the latter stem from societal organization, including elitism, urban-centric court locations, intimidating architecture, and fear of losing social support when asserting rights. International reports (FIDH 2023; Beqiraj, McNamara, 2014: 29–31) highlight further obstacles such as unequal economic status between parties, lack of expert testimony, and flawed evidentiary standards. In Poland, the comprehensive report by the Ombudsman’s Office (Błaszczak-Banasiak, Majdzińska, Zima-Parjaszewska, 2016) identifies dominant medicalized views of disability, lack of understanding of intellectual disability, ableism, and miscommunication as key barriers to justice.

4. Implementation of Article 13 CRPD Worldwide

With respect to the implementation of Article 13(1) and (2) of the CRPD, one of the most valuable comparative law sources is the documentation annexed to the report published on 27 December 2017 by the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), concerning the

status of implementation of Article 13 in the context of ensuring access to justice. Respondents to the OHCHR survey answered four core questions. Contributions were received from 25 governments, 17 national human rights institutions, 3 regional organizations, and 21 non-governmental organizations.

Most governmental responses included information on training programs for justice system personnel and police officers regarding the rights of persons with disabilities and effective communication with them. Educational initiatives were frequently cited, and many states emphasized the importance of removing communication barriers. Numerous reports also referenced efforts to eliminate architectural obstacles.

Below is a thematic overview of the most relevant information contained in these documents, followed by a summary of notable proposals. The degree of implementation varies significantly across jurisdictions. At the time of reporting, some countries had not yet initiated reforms to implement Article 13 (e.g., Armenia, Greece, Togo), while others were in the process of drafting legislation to expand access to justice (Nepal) or had only launched training initiatives (Montenegro, Turkey). In certain cases, implementation efforts were limited to criminal proceedings (Cyprus, Guatemala) or primarily focused on that domain (Germany).

As noted above, majority of government submissions to the OHCHR report emphasize the importance of training programs focused on the rights and specific needs of persons with disabilities, as well as on combating discrimination. Colombia stands out for its comprehensive approach: its justice sector training program spans 80 hours, with one of three core modules dedicated to access to justice. Notably, Colombia is the only country to have extended such training to all court personnel, including administrative and cleaning staff.

Several countries have developed collections of best practices, manuals, and practical guides aimed at improving accessibility. Among the most significant is the *Brasilia Regulations on Access to Justice for Vulnerable People*⁵, a set of 100 principles formulated by government delegations, judicial representatives, and legal professionals from many Ibero-American states. In Argentina, interdisciplinary teams have produced protocols recommending practices to enhance access to justice for persons with disabilities, illustrated with practical examples.

In Europe, the AJuPID project (Access to Justice for Persons with Intellectual

⁵ Reglas de Brasilia sobre el Acceso a la Justicia de las Personas en Condición de Vulnerabilidad, adopted at the Ibero-American Judicial Summit, Brasilia, 2008.

Disabilities) led to the creation of a compendium of “encouraging best practices” across six EU Member States. Spain has developed sector-specific guides, including a highly practical manual by the Madrid Bar Association for lawyers assisting persons with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities. The guide offers procedural accommodation strategies for interactions with clients or detainees, including recommendations on gesture use, emotional cues, repetition, avoiding corrections, and steering clear of open-ended, ambiguous, or overly complex questions and terminology. Spain’s national police have also published an extensive manual on engaging with persons with intellectual disabilities.

Colombia has issued a *Guide for Persons with Disabilities on Access to Justice*, developed by interministerial experts and civil society organizations. Mexico’s Supreme Court published a 138-page *Protocol for Justice Officials in Cases Involving the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*, alongside a detailed guide on drafting judgments in accessible and readable formats.

At the EU level, the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) released the *Handbook on European Law Relating to Access to Justice* in 2016, which includes Section 8.1 on persons with disabilities. The handbook highlights supportive tools such as written guides, reading assistants, professional sign language interpreters, and the provision of documents in accessible formats, including Braille and simplified versions. It also stresses the need for targeted training of court staff, police officers, and prison personnel.

It is noteworthy that several South American countries have introduced procedural accommodations not only for persons with disabilities but also for other vulnerable groups. In Peru, legal assistance procedures have been established for older persons, individuals with serious illnesses, and pregnant women. In Colombia, special protective measures have been adopted for women affected by internal armed conflict, as well as for displaced women with disabilities, elderly women, and female heads of household.

Some states have developed dedicated programs to advance access to justice. One example is the European AJuPID project “Access to Justice for Persons with Intellectual Disabilities”, co-funded by the European Commission. Its aim is to inform potential caregivers and justice system professionals about the rights of persons with intellectual disabilities and how to support them appropriately. Launched in April 2014, the AJuPID project involves ten partners from six European countries: Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Ireland, and Hungary. Additional multidisciplinary support programs have also been implemented for individuals facing social hardship.

South American countries have taken a leading role in developing structured programs to implement Article 13 of the CRPD. In 2011, Argentina pioneered the National Program for Assistance to Persons with Disabilities in their relations with the Justice System (ADAJUS), the first of its kind in Latin America, targeted at individuals receiving free legal aid. Chile’s National Service for Persons with Disabilities (SENADIS) has operated the “Access to Justice” program since 2015, in collaboration with bar associations, university legal clinics, and NGOs. It provides free legal assistance, sign language interpretation, and training for lawyers, judges, and police officers, with a focus on preventing discrimination and rights violations. Mexico has developed a framework for free legal advice and representation, while Peru launched its “National Plan for Access to Justice for Persons in Particularly Vulnerable Situations” in 2016, mandating implementation across 33 superior courts and emphasizing protections for older persons.

Globally, many countries have established monitoring bodies and conducted research on disability rights. The scope of legal capacity is often linked to the extent of implementation of Article 12 CRPD. In most jurisdictions, regardless of legal tradition, procedural capacity is tied to legal capacity (e.g., Armenia, France, Kenya, Kuwait, Portugal, Singapore, United Kingdom). However, several states grant procedural capacity to individuals with limited or no legal capacity in specific case types, particularly those concerning personal autonomy (e.g., Bulgaria, France, Latvia, Slovakia, Thailand). In Bulgaria, guardian consent is required to initiate proceedings; in Denmark, the guardian must obtain consent from the person represented. Colombia adopts a more inclusive model, granting procedural capacity by default unless the case concerns rights over which the individual lacks legal capacity. In some countries (e.g. Mexico and Germany), procedural capacity is presumed, and courts may appoint counsel or a guardian if doubts arise. Mixed models are also common (e.g. Denmark). Government reports frequently mention the provision of free interpretation services for persons with disabilities.

5. Implementation of Article 13 CRPD in Poland: Persistent Gaps in Civil Procedure

The UN Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities monitors the implementation of the Convention through reports submitted by state bodies, local authorities, and civil society organizations. Poland’s performance in implementing the CRPD has been consistently assessed as unsatisfactory, across medical, social, and legal domains. In its 2018 concluding

observations,⁶ the Committee identified serious deficiencies in the implementation of Article 13, particularly noting that persons with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities deprived of legal capacity are excluded from participating in civil proceedings and from testifying in court.

The Committee highlighted multiple barriers to access to justice in Poland, including the absence of procedural and communicative accommodations, physical inaccessibility of judicial buildings, lack of human rights-based training among justice and law enforcement personnel, and the absence of mechanisms for reporting violence – especially for persons in institutional care. It also criticized the lack of legal aid for persons with disabilities, particularly those with psychosocial impairments. The Committee issued detailed recommendations, urging Poland to guarantee supported and equal access to all judicial procedures, adapt procedural law, ensure alternative and augmentative communication, and provide free legal aid to low-income individuals with disabilities (CRDP, 2018: 3).

Despite these recommendations, civil procedure reform has been minimal. While some progress has been made in criminal proceedings, such as the 2024 amendment introducing tailored instructions and communication support for vulnerable participants, civil law remains largely unchanged. Two regulations have been adopted, but they are limited in scope and relevance. Planned reforms include exemptions from written testimony for certain persons with disabilities and the continuation of remote hearings, which proved beneficial during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Recent legislative proposals in civil and administrative procedure aim to improve the accessibility of oral and written instructions, including the use of Easy-to-Read formats and the involvement of sign language interpreters, communication assistants, and psychologists during hearings. However, these measures remain fragmented and insufficient. As the Committee noted in its 2019 report, Poland exhibits “critical stagnation” and a lack of political will to advance deinstitutionalization and ensure meaningful access to justice (RPO Biuletyn, 2019).⁷ The principle articulated by an Australian court remains instructive: accommodations are not a request for special treat-

⁶ CRPD (2018). Concluding observations on the initial report of Poland, UN Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 29.10.2018, https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/15/TreatyBodyExternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=CRPD%2FC%2FPOL%2FCO%2F1&Lang=en

⁷ RPO Biuletyn (2019). Rekomendacje Komitetu ONZ ds. Praw Osób z Niepełnosprawnościami dla Polski Warszawa, 17 maja 2019; <https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Wyst%C4%85pienie%20-%20Komisja%20Ekspert%C3%B3w%20ds.%20Os%C3%B3b%20Starszych%2017%20maja%202019.ppt>

ment, but a demand for equal access to services available to all⁸ (Gibson, 2010: 123-142).

6. Survey-Based Research on Communication Barriers and Procedural Equity in Civil Justice

In January and February 2025, the author conducted parallel survey-based research among judges and legal practitioners (advocates and legal advisors). The study aimed to explore: (1) communication challenges with persons with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities and older adults, along with techniques used to overcome these barriers; (2) perceptions of the balance between supporting vulnerable parties and maintaining equality of arms; and (3) the presence of stereotypes within the justice system, as identified in broader sociological and psychological research. The latter focus was prompted by Article 8(1)(b) of the CRPD, which mandates the elimination of stereotypes in all areas of life, a provision often overlooked.

The surveys examined training levels, communication techniques, and the practical application of procedural tools designed to support disadvantaged parties. References to specific survey questions appear throughout the study, while aggregate results are presented in the final chapter. To ensure relevance, the surveys excluded proceedings directly related to mental health status, such as guardianship or involuntary treatment cases. However, respondents with relevant experience in such matters could share insights in Section V of the questionnaire.

The judges' survey comprised 30 questions, with the final section inviting open-ended reflections and suggestions. Demographic data collected included gender, years of service, and court level. Sections II and III focused respectively on persons with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities and older adults, while Section IV addressed both groups. Most questions offered closed response options, typically using frequency or agreement scales. Some included an "Other" option for elaboration. The survey was distributed via court presidents to all levels of common courts in Poland.

The legal practitioners' survey mirrored the judges' version, with minor adjustments. Questions on judicial decision-making and court-appointed counsel without party request were removed, as the latter had been previously studied by the Bar Research Centre in 2024. Practitioners were uniquely asked whether professional bodies should develop communication guides. Terminology was slightly modified (e.g., "party" expanded to "party

⁸ Case *Eldridge v. British Columbia*, 1997, in: Gibson, 2010.

or client”). Demographic questions covered gender, professional title, and years of practice.

Advanced statistical analysis was outsourced to a specialized firm. The data were processed by Anna Milewska (Metodolog.pl, Konrad Hryniewicz Ltd.) using the Automated Statistical Description System SZTOS (Hryniewicz, Milewska, 2023).⁹

Findings confirm that individuals with cognitive impairments, including dementia, are increasingly present in legal practice and court proceedings. Given demographic trends, the justice system must prepare to ensure equal access beyond architectural accommodations.

Responses revealed widespread empathy and attentiveness among judges and lawyers. Many described techniques to reduce stress and improve recall, such as adjusting physical comfort and avoiding pressure. Nonetheless, the results clearly indicate a need for targeted training in communication tools and techniques for engaging persons with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities. Few respondents, especially among legal practitioners, had received training in alternative communication methods, suggesting non-compliance with Article 13(2) CRPD. Both groups broadly supported empowering courts to appoint counsel *ex officio* without a formal request or financial assessment. There was also strong support for introducing a *facilitator* role in civil proceedings to assist persons with disabilities in communicating with the court and other participants.

Judges overwhelmingly reported adapting their communication style to individual needs and seeking alternative means of engagement, including assistance from others present in the courtroom. This informal reliance on family members or counsel reinforces the case for formalizing the facilitator role. It also underscores the need for enhanced training for legal representatives, as required under Article 13(2) CRPD.

Despite the growing presence of clients with cognitive impairments, most lawyers do not use tools to simplify legal language. While AI may soon offer solutions, both judges and lawyers expressed skepticism about the effectiveness of oral instructions, especially for older adults with dementia. Many viewed them as superficial and overly complex. There was strong support for developing written guidance in plain language but opinions were divided

⁹ A. Milewska employed the following statistical tools in the analysis: the chi-square test for two variables (Pearson), Cramér’s V coefficient, the Mann–Whitney U test, Glass’s biserial correlation measure, the Kruskal–Wallis test for variable association, and Spearman’s rank correlation analysis.

on whether visual formats should be included; some feared infantilization, while others welcomed the idea.

Overall, the responses showed minimal divergence between the two professional groups. However, a notable difference emerged regarding whether cases involving older adults should be treated as urgent: most lawyers supported the idea, while judges largely opposed it, possibly due to concerns about frivolous litigation.

A majority of lawyers called for professional bodies to develop communication guides for working with clients with intellectual or psychosocial disabilities. There was also support for expanding judicial discretion and reducing procedural formalism in cases involving cognitive or communicative impairments.

Finally, while negative stereotypes about persons with psychosocial disabilities and older adults appear less prevalent in the legal community than in the general population, they are not entirely absent. This may reflect the continued lack of adequate training.

7. Conclusions

Article 13 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) marks a doctrinal turning point in international human rights law by recognizing *access to justice* as a distinct and autonomous right. This provision introduces a broader normative framework that encompasses organizational, communicative, and architectural dimensions of justice. The doctrinal evolution of access to justice underscores the imperative of interpreting Article 13 within a dynamic and socially responsive framework, capable of adapting to emerging legal needs and diverse forms of disadvantage. The CRPD's emphasis on *effective* access – rather than merely formal or theoretical availability – requires to adopt proactive measures ensuring meaningful participation of persons with disabilities in all stages of judicial proceedings.

In this context, the removal of communication barriers and the development of alternative communication methods have emerged as central priorities across jurisdictions. Particular attention has been directed toward the creation of practical guidelines for judges on drafting plain-language reasoning and for legal practitioners on accessible communication strategies. These initiatives reflect a growing recognition that linguistic complexity and procedural opacity can constitute *de facto* exclusions from justice systems.

Equally critical is the institutionalization of university-level academic programs dedicated to training interpreters in augmentative and alternative

communication methods. Such programs would not only enhance the professionalization of support services but also contribute to the long-term sustainability of inclusive justice infrastructures.

Innovative national practices further illustrate the operationalization of Article 13. The Peruvian judiciary's implementation of an internal IT system that automatically prioritizes cases involving older persons (based on the age of the party) represents a compelling model of age-sensitive adjudication. By embedding accessibility criteria into case management algorithms, such measures exemplify how technological tools can be harnessed to promote substantive equality.

Finally, the proposal to introduce the institution of a *support person* (facilitator) into civil proceedings warrants serious consideration. In less complex cases, such individuals could serve as informal interpreters, assisting parties in understanding judicial instructions and navigating procedural requirements. This model aligns with the CRPD's mandate to provide reasonable accommodation and could significantly enhance the procedural autonomy of litigants with cognitive or communicative impairments.

Taken together, these developments affirm that access to justice under Article 13 CRPD is not a static entitlement but a dynamic right that demands continuous normative refinement and practical innovation. The convergence of doctrinal clarity and institutional creativity will be essential to realizing the full promise of inclusive justice systems.

References

- Abregu M. (2001). Barricades or Obstacles: The Challenges of Access to Justice. In: Van Puymbroeck, R. V. (ed.), *Comprehensive Legal and Judicial Development: Toward an Agenda for a Just and Equitable Society in the 21st Century*. Washington: World Bank
- Bahdi R. (2007). Background Paper on Women's Access to Justice in the MENA Region. Cairo: UNDP
- Beqiraj J., McNamara L. (2014). International Access to Justice: Barriers and Solutions, Bingham: Centre for the Rule of Law, Report, 2.
- Błaszczak-Banasiak A., Majdzińska K., Zima-Parjaszewska M. (2016). Dostęp osób z niepełnosprawnościami do wymiaru sprawiedliwości – analiza i zalecenia. Warszawa: Biuro Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich
- Flynn E. (2016). *Disabled Justice? Access to Justice and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*. London/New York: Routledge

Garth B. G., Cappelletti M. (1978). Access to Justice: The Newest Wave in the Worldwide Movement to Make Rights Effective. *Buffalo Law Review*. 27.

Gibson F. (2010). Article 13 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities – a right to legal aid?, *Australian Journal of Human Rights*. 15(2).

Kowalczyk K. (2016). Przemoc wobec osób niepełnosprawnych. In: Krajewska-Kułak, E., Kowalczyk, K., Kułak-Bejda, A., Noz Guzowski, A., Kułak, W. (eds.), *Różne barwy przemocy*, Vol. I. Białystok: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Medycznego w Białymstoku

Lord J., Guernsey K. N., Balfe J. M., Karr V. L., Flowers N. (2012). *Human Rights: Yes! Action and Advocacy on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Human Rights Center

Palombella G. (2021). Access to Justice: Dynamic, Foundational, and Generative. *Ratio Juris*. 34.

Ruškus J. (2023). Transformative Justice for Elimination of Barriers to Access to Justice for Persons with Psychosocial or Intellectual Disabilities. *Laws*. 12.

International Law Acts

Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution A/RES/61/106, 13 December 2006, entered into force on 3 May 2008.

European Convention on Human Rights, signed in Rome on 4 November 1950, entered into force on 3 September 1953, Council of Europe, ETS No. 5.

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution 2200A (XXI), 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976.

Reglas de Brasilia sobre el Acceso a la Justicia de las Personas en Condición de Vulnerabilidad, adopted at the Ibero-American Judicial Summit, Brasilia, 2008.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, Resolution 217 A (III), 10 December 1948.

Other sources

CRPD. (2018). Concluding observations on the initial report of Poland, UN Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 29.10.2018, retrieved 10 August 2025 from https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/15/Treaty-

BodyExternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=CRPD%2FC%2FPOL%2-FCO%2F1&Lang=en

FIDH. (2023). Overcoming Barriers to Access to Justice for Victims of Corporate Human Rights Abuses, https://www.fidh.org/IMG/pdf/access_to_justice_joint_brief_july_2023_.pdf, retrieved 3 August 2025.

Hryniewicz K., Milewska A. (2023). SZTOS: System Zautomatyzowanego Tworzenia Opisu Statystycznego (Wersja SZTOS 2023) [Oprogramowanie], <https://sztos-it.com/>

RPO Biuletyn. (2019). Rekomendacje Komitetu ONZ ds. Praw Osób z Niepełnosprawnościami dla Polski Warszawa, 17 maja 2019, <https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Wyst%C4%85pnie%20-%20Komisja%20Ekspert%C3%B3w%20ds.%20Os%C3%B3b%20Starszych%2017%20maja%202019.ppt>, retrieved 4 August 2025.

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**ПРИМЕНА ЧЛАНА 13. КОНВЕНЦИЈЕ О ПРАВИМА ОСОБА СА
ИНВАЛИДИТЕТОМ У СВЕТЛУ ИСКУСТАВА ДРЖАВА УГОВОРНИЦА**

Резиме

Конвенција о правима особа са инвалидитетом (*UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006*) је први међународни правни документ који експлицитно препознаје право на приступ правди као посебно људско право. Конвенција прописује обавезу држава уговорница да уведу адекватне процедуре и решења како би се особама са инвалидитетом обезбедио равноправан и ефикасан приступ правди, укључујући и адекватне услове прилагођене старосној доби особе са инвалидитетом. У раду се најпре разматрају концептуални оквири приступа правди и препреке које онемогућавају остваривање права на приступ правди. Затим се даје преглед неких решења у одабраним државама уговорницама која имају за циљ да особама са инвалидитетом обезбеде равноправан и ефикасан приступ правди. У последњем делу рада ауторка даје преглед резултата истраживања о проблемима са којима се судије и адвокати у Пољској суочавају у комуникацији са особама са инвалидитетом. Примена члана 13 Конвенције о правима особа са инвалидитетом је и даље незадовољавајућа у многим државама. По мишљењу ауторке, међународна размена искустава у примени Конвенције може послужити као извор инспирације за земље које тек треба да уведу процесне и друге гаранције и изврше адекватна прилагођавања, како би особама са инвалидитетом осигурале ефикасан приступ правди. Треба напоменути да нека ефикасна решења захтевају минимална финансијска улагања.

Кључне речи: приступ правди, препреке, Конвенција о правима особа са инвалидитетом, судски поступак, процесне гаранције и прилагођавање потребама.